

THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO UPGRADE THE TEA DESTINATION OF DARJEELING AND ITS EFFECT ON LOCAL COMMUNITIES – A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Digital tools for information storage, dissemination, and customization were quickly embraced by the travel and tourism sector. Centralized reservation systems and global distribution networks are two such instances. Even more, local communities may benefit from more chances to advertise their tourism resources, create novel goods, establish their own enterprises, and bring in more visitors and foreign currency via the use of ICT technologies. Similarly, technology has the potential to promote micro-enterprise tourism, which helps reduce poverty and protects cultural and natural sites. Local companies benefit from and are promoted by micro-enterprise tourism.

The sweet scent of tea leaves, the gorgeous green tea farms, the magnificent valley covered with curling clouds, and the tinkling of mountain streams have attracted nature lovers from across the globe for centuries. The offering of tea, the world's most popular beverage, is universally seen as a kind gesture, whether it is made in a private household or by a commercial hospitality service. One of the oldest forms of tourism, tea tourism also offers a resource that may be utilised by the hospitality sector. In print, "tea tourism" is defined as "the art of travelling the globe in quest of the pleasure received from exposure to vast green tea fields." Many tour operators from different parts of the world have capitalised on the growing interest in tea by offering trips to tea plantations. Some visitors to China spend several glorious days at a tea plantation, staying in a quaint hut and seeing workers pick, wither, roll, and finish their teas in front of them. Emerging economies like India, Nepal, China, Sri Lanka, and Japan are attracting an increasing number of tourists who are interested in tea, and these countries all provide both unique and mass-market experiences in the tea industry. Sustainable tourism like that practised by community-based attractions promotes local autonomy and independence.

Keywords: Digital tools, Tea destination, Local communities, Regression analysis

INTRODUCTION

Community-based tourism (CBT) is a kind of tourism that originated in the 1980s as an appealing alternative to more traditional forms of mass tourism as a method of encouraging local development. CBT is an acronym for community-based tourism. It has been acknowledged as a

model for the production of tourism-related products and services that satisfy the social, environmental, and financial requirements of the communities in which they are situated. Community-based treatments, sometimes known as CBT, are one type of enterprise-based resource management that is conducted on a community level (Sarkar, 2015). Residents of these kinds of communities have a significant amount of power over the tourism sector and stand to benefit significantly from their involvement in it. Community-based tourism, also known as CBT, is a strategy that is developed via the engagement of the local community. This is in contrast to the more traditional style of tourism, which is known as mass tourism. (Gurău, 2018) Because of this, the city has a higher amount of wiggle room to develop its products that are connected to tourism.

Darjeeling, in West Bengal, is widely regarded as one of the most beautiful hill resorts in all of the globe. Its views of snow-capped peaks, the tranquilly of brilliant green hills enveloped in splendour, and a sight of spectacular beauty topped by the massive Himalayas all serve to entice young people, those with an adventurous spirit, and enthusiasts of all ages. The region's tourist spots and attractions are serene and untouched, and they serve as a centre for tourism that focuses on adventure, leisure, and specialised interests. The Toy Train, which is a World Heritage Site, tea tourism, river rafting, hiking, bird watching tours, butterfly viewing tours, forest safaris, and wellness tourism are among the most popular tourist activities in the region. Tea tourism may be carried out either for commercial or recreational purposes. There is a connection between commercial tea tourism and business travel. In order for the business to analyse the growth of local farmers and industries, the corporation will foot the bill for the trip. This collection is useful for gaining knowledge about some of the brands that are used as well as distinctive strategies for the cultivation of tea.

"Tea tourism" is tourism that is "driven by an interest in the history, culture, and usage of tea," according to one definition of the term. In addition to partaking in significant rites and events, travellers may also learn about the local customs by seeing significant landmarks (such as farms and museums) and walking agricultural pathways. People go there not just to see where tea first originated but also to immerse themselves in the extensive history and culture associated with the beverage. The undulating landscapes of the tea gardens themselves are the key draw for tourists interested in tea. A well-kept tea garden, complete with tea plants and trees that provide shade, has the potential to be a veritable feast for the eyes. The following are some of the economic effects of tea tourism: The Darjeeling tea business is continuously growing while while preserving its dominant position on the global tea market. A significant role in the modern economy of many nations has been taken up by tourism as a result of its ability to both generate foreign cash and provide support for national economies. The expansion of tea tourism will be beneficial to the state in reducing insurgency and other socioeconomic challenges. These benefits will accrue to the state as a result of the industry's positive impact on the environment, the protection of cultural and historical heritage, and the growth of rural economies. Tea tourism has the ability to create significant cash for the government and to change the region's position on the tourist map of the globe if it is pushed with sound planning and possibilities.

The industry of tea tourism in Darjeeling is still in its infancy despite its rapid growth. A growing number of tea plantations are treated as honoured guests in the gardens and residences of their

owners. In the past, only estate directors and the family of the estate owners were allowed to live on tea plantations. In addition to providing lodging, a wide range of activities, such as nature and village hikes, eco-adventure activities, exposure to tea garden life and regional culture, sightseeing excursions, organic cuisine, and so on, are being made available to participants. This not only provides an extra source of revenue for the management, but it also increases the number of employment prospects for the villagers who work in tea garden retreats and other activities related with the tea gardens. The village residents and gardeners who choose to remodel their homes in order to host visitors at their homes will get additional compensation as a result of the home stays. Overall, the tea tourism industry is fairly disorganised.

Where exactly is the city of Darjeeling situated? Due to the tight standards that the tea plantation owners have for the selection of tourists, there are not many tour operators and travel firms that are operating in the tea tourism industry. Although Darjeeling is wonderful for tourists, the overwhelming bulk of the immense potential it has is yet not fully utilised. However, because of the rise in the number of tourists and the development of new building, the natural resources of the area are now being put under a tremendous lot of stress and are very susceptible to environmental damage. The tourism industry in this area is very seasonal, which exposes the community's precarious economic situation, particularly during the off-season when there are few available jobs. Strong strategy and planning are required across the whole area in order to make the most of the existing tourism business. Even if the development of tourism in the hilly regions of Darjeeling is essential, it should not take place at the expense of the natural balance. Therefore, "Development without Destruction" is the only path to a solution for global peace that can be maintained over the long term. As a consequence of this, it is legitimate to say that the role that tourism plays in the hill districts of Darjeeling has to be reevaluated. The inhabitants, in conjunction with the appropriate authorities, should subsequently take the required procedures. In Darjeeling Hills, tourism is a significant business that is seeing rapid expansion smoke-free. The fundamental role of information and communications technology (ICT) is to connect people, companies, and resources. Online payment platforms such as PayPal, Stripe, Amazon Pay, and Alipay are revolutionising the financial industry. Sharing economy platforms such as Uber, Airbnb, and Airtasker have disrupted industries that are closely related to their own. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter have fundamentally altered how individuals communicate with one another (Murisi, 2016). As a direct consequence of the platforms, there has been a considerable shakeup in the corporate structures of their respective economic sectors. This has led to significant new opportunities. As a direct consequence of the proliferation of information and communication technology (TIC) applications, it is anticipated that sustainable CBT would extend into rural and undeveloped regions of emerging countries (Warner, 2019). It is possible that the provision of tourism services to more distant places will be of considerable assistance to both the expansion of small settlements and the number of employment that are available in such areas (Yoon, 2020). to encourage tourism-related firms to make a positive contribution to the financial and social well-being of the communities in which they are located. However, there is a dearth of research that investigates the function of information and communications technologies (ICTs) in the production and promotion of ecologically conscious and community-based tourism offers (Burgos, 2017). As a direct consequence of this, the majority of the benefits are distributed to the native population. The purpose of the CBT is to

offer locals and tourists with something of value by drawing attention not only to the economic benefits of the area, but also to the need of ecological preservation and locally pertinent social concerns (Rasoolimanesh, 2017).

In 2018, the United States welcomed a record-breaking 1.4 billion tourists from other countries, which was a 6 percent increase from the previous year. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of individuals from all areas of life who are interested in travelling the world (Zhao, 2015). When compared to the previous year, 2015 saw a decrease in the number of tourists from other countries that travelled to developing nations. It is anticipated that by the year 2030, developing economies would be visited by 58% of all international visitors. In addition to this, tourism is a significant source of revenue for a great number of countries that are considered to be developing (Duffett, 2017).

The ceremony of preparing and drinking tea has a significant place in the history of many cultures and communities all over the globe. Locals have been able, for a considerable amount of time now, to ensure their financial futures via a combination of tourism and the production and consumption of tea. "Tea tourism" is a sector of the tourism industry that places a focus on environmental preservation, responsible business practises, and a zeal for the great outdoors (Zamani, 2017). On the other hand, there is a dearth of published information on tea tourism. Experts have, over the course of many years, repeatedly emphasised the significance of tea in the provision of hospitality, the enhancement of customer pleasure, and the delivery of high-quality services; however, additional research is required to properly comprehend its significance in order to fully appreciate its impact (Parker, 2016).

The potential for tourism to have a detrimental impact on the environment, sociocultural values, and the economic repercussions of rising expenses of living may be mitigated by the practise of sustainable tourism, which may offer local communities with shared value and benefits (Bidemi, 2017). Therefore, community-based entrepreneurship, which is a type of social entrepreneurship, is inextricably related to the local culture, which might vary significantly from one location to the next. The idea of a "community entrepreneur" arose as part of a framework for the pioneering of social change. According to this conceptualization, the term "community entrepreneur" refers to a leader of a group who is capable of fostering more cooperation between the community and nonprofit organisations (O'Klein, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Multiple studies have shown a correlation between personal usage of information and communication technologies and greater GDP. Using data gathered from emerging countries between 1993 and 2015, academics, for example, have explored the link between technical innovation, educational performance, and economic growth. Countries with a gross primary enrolment rate of 92.53 percent or above saw their economic development improve by 0.224 percentage points for every percentage point increase in internet access (Asongu, 2020). Therefore, a sufficient level of knowledge was required for there to be economic growth as a result of the internet. The authors also carried out Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), and Granger causality tests using panel data obtained from developing countries between the years 1995 and 2015. By doing so, he created a cyclical connection between online engagement and the accumulation of wealth (proxied by GDP per capita). Because of their individual usage of information and

communication technology, it has been hypothesised that high school students in developing countries have more opportunities to study and access to a greater choice of subject matter to pick from than students in developed nations (ICTs). It was believed that giving students in less developed countries the opportunity to study with and through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) would be an effective method of supporting progress in such countries (Gash, 2017).

The application of information and communications technology (ICT) may result in improvements to a company's competitive edge, productivity, and efficiency; all three aspects are vital to sustaining business growth. Studies have shown that the use of information and communication technologies in developing nations may reduce the amount of time and money necessary to launch a business, which in turn can lead to an increase in the total number of businesses (Sulong, 2016). It is a widely held belief that the growth of information and communication technologies inspires creativity, which in turn results in the production of resources that make people's lives easier (Falco, 2017). According to a variety of sources, the widespread use of mobile phones bolsters the information technology sector and enhances supply chain management, both of which are beneficial to telecommunications corporations. In addition to this, the efficiency of other systems, such as the economic system, the medical system, and the academic system, is improved as a result of their implementation. The adoption of e-application commerce into business operations has the potential to stimulate economic development across all different types of companies. This is due to the fact that the prospective advantages of e-application commerce may be used by companies of varying sizes. E-commerce is something that Asian businesses absolutely have to get on board with if they want to stay competitive. The broad use of digital technology, such as digital monitoring and digital exchange of commodities, has been credited with contributing to the Rwandan tea industry's administrative and operational efficiencies, which have increased significantly as a result (Andersson, 2019).

It is very necessary for the economic growth of a region. As a direct result of this, the local populace's way of life as well as their opinions shift. This is only feasible with skilled administration, growth, and coordination of the tourism industry. The tourist business is still in its infancy despite the fact that it has a tremendous deal of potential. However, while being the most accessible resource in the area, it is also the one that gets used the least. However, the majority of the tourism industry is concentrated in Darjeeling due to the city's abundance of naturally stunning locations. Darjeeling has been a popular location for tourists even since the days when it was colonised by the British. In addition to that, it developed into a resort with a spa. Visitors are drawn to the region because of its enormous expanse of scenic beauty and grandeur, its stunning view of the majestic snow-capped mountains with projecting peaks, its thrilling climate, its diversity and abundance of flora and fauna, and its rushing streams. The region's tourist spots and attractions are serene and untouched, and they serve as a centre for tourism that focuses on adventure, leisure, and specialised interests.

The rising rates are a significant source of frustration for vacationers who are there during the high season. Not only are critical supplies difficult to come by, but retailers are also demanding exorbitant prices from customers. Even hotel rates are subject to change depending on the level of demand. The prices charged by private transportation service providers are higher, and they transport a greater number of passengers than their vehicles are able to hold. The quality of the service provided by the hotel is gradually diminishing, which is having an impact on its most

valuable clientele. The porters and guides quickly raise their prices in response to the opportunity. As a direct result of this, visitors leave with a negative image, which might sometimes lead to social unrest and isolated crimes. Even though the vast majority of people see tourism as a potential source of revenue, it is abundantly clear that the assets associated with tourism do not belong to the people. When it comes to providing a warm welcome, the residents of the plains either own or lease these hotels. Because there are either extremely few or no individuals who work in the tourist industry in rural regions, the topic of their income is meaningless. Additionally, because there are very few or no people who work in the tourism business in rural areas. The only ones who benefit from this are travel agents.

OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of the study is to understand the application of digital technologies to upgrade the tea destination of Darjeeling. Hence in order to measure the overall upgradation of tea destination, due to the limitation of time, the researchers focuses to investigate using three main variables which are: Entrepreneurship opportunities available through digital technologies due to the tea tourism in Darjeeling; enable in generating better return on investment for the importers and exporters of Tea in the area and the overall upliftment and support in developing communities in Darjeeling.

The expansionary effects of digital tools may be amplified by a skilled labour force and a governmental environment that promotes information and communications technology (ICT). The quality of human capital has been highlighted in previous research as an important supplementary component in the study of the correlation between ICT and economic growth. As a consequence of this, investing in human capital is an essential component of policy that needs to be addressed in order to maximise the positive effects that ICT has on economic growth. As a consequence of this, consumers as a whole would develop into the primary drivers of digitization on the continent. This would put pressure on businesses to make greater use of technology in order to fulfil the expectations of India's rapidly expanding population of tech-savvy consumers. The government could also take steps to increase the variety of mobile applications available, which, among other things, would make it easier to engage in activities such as distance learning. In spite of the fact that our data have shown a rising trend in digitalization ever since 2012, the Indian government ought to establish appropriate science, technology, and innovation (STI) policies in order to increase the utilisation of digital technology as well as technical expertise.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The authors of the study obtained the data necessary for their research from a variety of sources, including primary and secondary sources. Many secondary sources, such as EBSCO, Google Scholar, and others, were consulted for this study. In addition, in order to obtain important data for the study, the researchers employed a questionnaire with closed-ended questions. A convenience sample was used to select approximately 150 respondents, of which 146 finished filling out the questionnaires in their entirety. The authors performed two principal analyses, a correlation analysis and a regression analysis, using the data that was obtained via SPSS.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This part is focused in analysing the data analysis based on the responses received from the

respondents.

Table 1: Digital tools support sustainable growth

Digital tools support sustainable growth	Frequency	Percent
Highly important	10	6.8
Important	8	5.5
Moderately important	20	13.7
Not so important	39	26.7
Not at all important	69	47.3
Total	146	100

Based on Table 1 analysis it is noted that nearly 47.3% of the respondents have stated that using digital tools enable in supporting sustainable growth in the tea industry in Darjeeling., also 26.7% have mentioned as important. However, 13.7% specified as moderately important to the statement, 5.5% have stated that it is not so important and 6.8% have mentioned as not at all important.

Fig 1: Digital tools support sustainable growth

Table 2: Digital technologies enhance employment opportunities

Digital technologies enhance employment	Frequency	Percent
Highly important	10	6.8
Important	15	10.3
Moderately important	18	12.3
Not so important	60	41.1
Not at all important	43	29.5
Total	146	100

Based on the table 2 output it is identified that 41.1% of the respondents have mentioned that Digital technologies enhance employment opportunities as highly important. Moreover, 29.5% of the respondents have stated as important. However, 12.3% were mentioned it as moderately important to the statement, 10.3% of them were stating as not so important and remaining were stating it to be not at all important.

Fig2: Digital technologies enhance employment opportunities

Correlation analysis

The third part is focused to analyse the independent variable: Entrepreneurship opportunities; Better return on investment and Support in developing communities and dependent variable: Upgrade tea destination

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

Correlations	Entrepreneurship opportunities	Better return on investment	Support in developing communities	Upgrade tea destination
Entrepreneurship opportunities	1	0.889	0.824	0.859
Better return on investment	0.889	1	0.859	0.868
Support in developing communities	0.824	0.859	1	0.825
Upgrade tea destination	0.859	0.868	0.825	1

The analysis shows a highest association lies between Better return on investment and Upgrade tea destination with value of +0.868, those shows that there exist high positive correlation between them, furthermore other variables like Entrepreneurship opportunities and Upgrade tea destination with value + 0.859 and Support in developing communities and Upgrade tea destination with value of +0.825

Regression Analysis

The last section is to understand the mode of understanding between variables, hence regression analysis is used

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Analysis	SS	Free.	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	142.72	3.00	47.57	192.36	0.00
Residual	35.12	142.00	0.25		
Regression Analysis	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.32	0.16		1.96	0.05
Entrepreneurship opportunities	0.35	0.08	0.35	4.18	0.00
Better return on investment	0.34	0.09	0.37	3.94	0.00
Support in developing communities	0.21	0.07	0.22	2.92	0.00
Co-eff of determination	0.80				

From the table it is noted that the F value is 192.36 with p value of 0.00, hence can be concluded that it is statistically significant. Also, the equation is stated as follows

Upgrade tea destination = 0.32 + 0.35 x Better return on investment + 0.34 x Better return on investment + 0.21 x Support in developing communities.

DISCUSSION

CBT offers amazing business potential to local citizens in underdeveloped nations, which is especially beneficial given the upward increase in the number of tourists visiting these areas. It has been the subject of research conducted by focus groups indicating visitors who go to developing nations would rather take part in activities that are uniquely native to the area than just visit tourist sites. Opportunities for tourism could present themselves in emerging nations like Nepal that have a population that is comprised of many different ethnic groups. Communities, tourism service providers, and local governments will be able to use a digital platform to plan, process, and offer cutting-edge tourism products and services that are in line with the triple bottom line (social, environmental, and economic) in order to have a positive social impact on a particular community. This will allow for tourism to have a positive effect on the community in question.

CONCLUSION

Recent years have seen a rise in the number of tourists visiting Darjeeling, which may be attributed to the many development projects undertaken by the Hill Development Programme. The two types of travellers that are the most common are domestic tourists and tourists from other countries. The number of foreign visitors that came to Darjeeling from outside of India was quite low. Since the fighting along the Sino-Indian border in 1962, the number of foreign tourists allowed to go to this area has been severely limited. There is no information that can be found on the precise amount of non-natives. On the other hand, it is a fact that their total population grows each year. The countries of Germany, Canada, the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Japan, and Australia each provide a significant proportion of the world's visitors. In addition to these visitors from other countries, Darjeeling also receives a sizeable influx of tourists from

inside India each and every year. It is exceedingly difficult to gather estimates of the number of people travelling inside their own country since there are no established norms or procedures for recording their journeys. The characteristics that draw tourists to the Darjeeling Hills have started to erode as a consequence of the excessive increase of tourism, particularly in urban areas. This is especially true in urban areas. In order to solve this scenario, it is imperative that a part of the incoming tourist traffic be diverted to various other Darjeeling Himalayan regions by developing flourishing tourism in those locations. This may be accomplished by boosting vibrant tourism in the respective regions. April, May, June, and October are the months that see the greatest visitors to Darjeeling from the tourist industry. These four months account for between sixty and seventy percent of the total number of tourists who visit Darjeeling every year. The city of Darjeeling feels the most strain from the influx of visitors at this time of year. The mobility fleet operated by the tourism department offers visitors a helpful service throughout the whole year. They provide visitors travelling between Bagdogra and the NJP Railway station with the option to take a bus to Darjeeling and back. In addition, there are plans to provide guided trips to Mirik and other local sightseeing opportunities in the Darjeeling area.

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